

The lexical and syntactical study of idioms

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Abstract

Idioms are the expressions the elements of which cannot be changed or replaced by other elements. They are called fixed expressions. The article deals with the lexical and syntactic features of idioms. Different linguistic and cognitive approaches by different scholars have been analyzed in the article, and the proper conclusions have been made.

In A First Dictionary of Linguistics and Phonetics (1980) and in The Cambridge Encyclopedia of the English Language (2003), Crystal defines idioms as: ‘A term used in grammar and lexicology to refer to a sequence of words which is semantically and often syntactically restricted, so that they function as a single unit. From a semantic viewpoint, the meaning of the individual words cannot be summed to produce the meaning of the ‘idiomatic’ expression as a whole. From a syntactic viewpoint, the words often do not permit the usual variability they display in other context, e.g. *it’s raining cats and dogs* does not permit **it’s raining a cat and a dog/dogs and cats, etc.*’ (Crystal, 1980:179 as cited in Awwad, 1990:57) 7 ‘Two central features identify an idiom. The meaning of the idiomatic expression cannot be deduced by examining the meanings of the constituent lexemes. And the expression is fixed, both grammatically and lexically. Thus, *put a sock in it!* means ‘stop talking’ and it is not possible to replace any of the lexemes and retain the idiomatic meaning. *Put a stocking in it or put a stock on it* must be interpreted literally or not at all.’ (Crystal, 2003:163)

People express and share their thought and emotions, their wish and intentions by using the language. Syntax combines words in a sentence; however, knowledge of grammar is not good enough to know a language as a whole because language contains lots of idiomatic constructions which require both theoretical and practical knowledge.

Idioms are usually investigated to seek out ways of understanding the possibility of transformations in some idioms and stability of the others which do not undergo any changes. Different viewpoints have been considered in study of idioms some of which have

found their reflections in a variety of scientific publications. Scholars claim that the unity of semantics and syntax helps to understand and analyze idioms efficiently. Attempts have been made to discover the relation between form and meaning and define the possible syntactic changes, transformations within idioms. Moreover, the lexical and syntactical analyses are carried out from the cognitive point of view.

Moreover, any grammatical form predicts of what a meaning consists, it means that every grammar form differs from the language rules which we establish a sentence, and the one not corresponding to the grammar rules turns to an exceptional form. In this case it should be learned and investigated as a whole construction. Existence of such constructions is the main condition of the existence of combinations which are called idioms.

The first Transformational Generative attempt to deal with idioms was developed by Katz and Postal in their short article entitled ‘Semantic Interpretation of Idioms and The Sentences Containing Them’. In it, idioms are considered to be the ‘exceptions that prove the rule’ of compositionality since they do not get their meaning from the meanings of their syntactic parts. Thus, if an idiom is treated as if it were compositional, false predictions are made about its semantic properties and relations. To emphasize the non-compositional meaning of idioms, the authors offer the following definition: ‘The essential feature of an idiom is that its full meaning, and more generally the meaning of any sentence containing an idiomatic stretch, is not a compositional function of the meanings of the idiom’s elementary grammatical parts.’¹⁷

According to Katz then, idioms are syntactically complex concatenations in a language that consist of two or more morphemes that the semantic component of the grammar treats as lexical items and are entered as unanalyzed wholes in the semantic dictionary. The dictionary should now be thought of as having two parts, a lexical-item part and a phrase-idiom part that consists of both lexical idioms such as compound words (e.g. telephone, baritone), noun + adjective (e.g. snow-white), verb + particle (e.g. put up) and similar clusters and phrasal idioms like verb + object groups (e.g. kick the bucket)¹⁸. Entries in the latter part will have the form: first, a particular string of morphemes, the idiomatic stretch;

¹⁷ Katz, J.J. and P.M. Postal. Semantic Interpretation of Idioms and Sentences containing them. M.I.T. Research Laboratory of Electronics Quarterly Progress Report 70. 1963. pp. 275-282.

¹⁸ Katz, J.J. Compositionality, Idiomaticity and Lexical Substitution. In S. Anderson and P. Kiparsky (Eds.) A Festschrift for Morris Halle. New York: Holt, Rinehart and Winston. 1973. pp. 357-376.

next, some associated constituent that must dominate the idiomatic stretch in the phrase markers that are to be assigned the semantic information associated with the pair of the idiomatic stretch and its dominating constituent, and, finally, the semantic information itself.

It is important to mark that syntax establishes the coordinated system of form and meaning. Any thought in the language can be expressed in different forms. Sometimes two semantic descriptions in a sentence appear: real or concrete, idiomatic or figurative. Without depending on the sameness of the syntactic structure, the carried-out analysis in the same sentence basing on the context shows itself differently. As a result of this, the same form, the same syntactic structure attains different meanings. We may describe the connection of form and meaning in syntax on the example of the idiom “He has deep pockets” (“to be able to afford a lot of expensive things”) as follows:

As it is obviously seen, within the sentence (“He has deep pockets”) depending upon the form the words possess distinctive syntactic functions.

While describing an idiom its internal specific features must be taken into consideration. The element of idioms cannot be regarded as lexical units. The function which an idiom carries out within a sentence is equal to the function of a single word in the sentence. As an ordinary word an idiom can’t be broken into parts in a sentence, neither can be changed. Despite this, it is possible to create a new lexical unit from the words, but on

the ground of idioms new combinations cannot be established. Words possess independent meanings, but as the words constituting idioms lose their independence of meaning, the meaning of idioms is not given in the separately-taken words, but the whole idiom expresses the meaning as that of one word. A word is an ordinary realization of meaning, but an idiom is its figurative expression. Words united with one another may form a compound, but it doesn't mean that any compounding is an idiom. The form, syntactic features and meaning are what make lexical units and idioms identical. Idioms differ from lexical units only in not possessing morphological structure as the construction is taken as a whole. Highlighting all these features, we stress the fact that during the general analysis of a sentence containing an idiom the whole idiomatic construction must be analyzed as a single word, and question to the whole construction must be put just in the same way as the question directed to a word. Without depending on the number of the words in the sentence, the unity of the syntactic function of an idiom is the major feature characterising it. So, we may name the idiom as a syntactic unit, possessing lexical wholeness. Such syntactic units belong to phraseology and are studied within phraseology.

Adam Makkai in his scientific article so-called 'Idiom structure in English' differentiates between idioms of encoding and idioms of decoding. He describes idioms of encoding as "phraseological peculiarities" which do not involve misunderstanding, unintelligibility, the ability to mislead, or ambiguity. He points out that in many European languages, for instance, one drives with a certain speed (French *avec une certaine vitesse*, German *mit einer gewissen Geschwindigkeit*), whereas the English usage is drive at a certain speed. Idioms of encoding is the term used to refer to the natural way of using a language. According to Makkai (1972:25), idioms of decoding are "genuine, or semantic idioms". These idioms involve potential misunderstanding, unintelligibility, the ability to mislead, and ambiguity. All idioms of decoding are also idioms of encoding, but not necessarily vice versa. For instance, the expression hot potato ("embarrassing issue") is an idiom of decoding, since it could mislead a hearer to think that the speaker is referring to a food item at a high temperature. It is also an idiom of encoding, insofar as that is what English speakers say when talking about an embarrassing issue and not, for example, tight shoes, burning chestnut, or a porcupine in your hands (Makkai, 1972:25). Makkai's

treatment of idioms focuses on idioms of decoding. Makkai proposes a structural framework based on a stratified view of language in which the term idiom is reserved for two phenomena, viz. lexemic and sememic idioms. Each of these represents a specific idiomaticity area in the English language. Entering into the intricacies of stratificational linguistics is beyond the scope of the present study, and I will therefore restrict my attention to the two idiomaticity areas that Makkai singles out. The first idiomaticity area is on what Makkai calls the lexemic stratum. According to him (1972:122), a lexemic idiom is “any polylexonic lexeme which is made up of more than one minimal free form or word (as defined by morphotactic criteria), each lexon of which can occur in other environments as the realization of a monolexonic lexeme”. This basically means that a lexemic idiom is a multi-word expression whose constituent elements can occur independently in other contexts. He mentions (1972:122-123) three types of elements which are compulsory in the expressions where they occur, viz. (1) singular and plural morphemes¹⁸ such as *s* in *hammer* and *tongs*; (2) the conjunction *and* in binomials such as *hammer and tongs*; and (3) articles such as *a* in *to pull a fast one*. These elements are not subject to the requirement that they be able to occur independently in other contexts,¹⁹ nor do they ever realise any meanings other than for instance “plural”, “additive conjunction”, or “definite article”. Apart from these exceptions, according to Makkai’s main definition, all the words in a multi-word expression must be able to occur independently in other environments as the realisation of a minimal lexical unit if that particular multi-word expression is to be considered idiomatic. This seems like quite a roundabout way of saying that idioms are multi-word expressions. Makkai’s definition begs the question as to what constitutes the difference between (lexemic) idioms and any other multi-word expression. He points out (1972:122) that the difference between lexemic idioms and other multi-word expressions lies in the fact that lexemic idioms are subject to possible misunderstanding, even though the listener is familiar with the meanings of the components, or to erroneous decoding. It is clear that he regards ambiguity as central to the notion of idiomaticity — or at least of lexical idioms. Multi-word expressions containing one or more elements which do not occur independently in other environments are not ambiguous and are therefore not idioms. Makkai (1972:123) calls this type of expression pseudo-idioms, e.g. *to and fro* (*fro* does not occur elsewhere as an independent

word and is therefore not ambiguous). According to Makkai (1972:124), expressions whose meaning can be deduced from the meanings of their constituent elements are not idioms but literal constitutes, e.g. spaghetti and meatballs.

After discussing the characteristics of the two two idiomaticity areas, Makkai (1972:135-179) describes the most important types of English lexemic and sememic idioms, of which a schematic representation is offered as follows:

Lexemic idioms

Types	Description	Examples
1. Phrasal verb idioms	v. + prep./adv. (+ prep.)	<i>put up, get back at</i>
2. Tournure idioms	polylexonic lexeme larger than phrasal	<i>have it in for</i>
<i>Subclasses:</i>	a) v. + <i>it</i> + adv.	<i>have it out (with)</i>
	b) compulsory nonrepresentative <i>it</i> last in sequence	<i>come off it</i>
	c) with nonrepresentative def. art.	<i>fly off the handle</i>
	d) with nonrepresentative indef. art.	<i>pull a fast one</i>
	e) v. + irreversible binomial	<i>rain cats and dogs</i>
	f) prep. + irreversible binomial	<i>through thick and thin</i>
	v. + dir. obj. + optional modifiers (no <i>it, a, the</i>)	<i>cash in one's chips</i>
	v. + modifier (no dir. obj.)	<i>dance on air</i>
	forms headed by <i>be</i> (may be conjugated)	<i>be up a creek</i>
3. Irreversible	parts A and B joined by a finite	<i>salt and pepper</i>

binomial idioms	set of links	
<i>Subclasses:</i>	i. morphotactically irreversible binomials	<i>ups and downs</i> <i>(*downs and ups)</i>
	ii. morphotactically reversible binomials	<i>cloak-and-dagger</i> (idiom) vs. <i>dagger and cloak</i> (separate items)
	iii. tournure doublets	<i>rain cats and dogs vs. rain dogs and cats</i>
	iv. multinominals	<i>Tom, Dick and Harry</i>
Phrasal compound idioms		<i>Bookworm</i>
Incorporating verb idioms	complex lexemes whose 1 st lexon is a n. or adj. in other environments; literal encoding reveals a related structure: v.+ dir. obj. / PP	<i>Eavesdrop</i>
<i>Patterns:</i>	a) n.-v.	<i>baby-sit</i>
	b) adj.-n.	<i>Blackmail</i>
	c) n.-n.	<i>Mastermind</i>
	d) adj.-v.	<i>Blacklist</i>

Pseudo-idioms	lexemic idioms containing a cranberry morph	<i>kith and kin</i>
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Sememic idioms

Types	Description	Examples
1. “First base” idioms	based on nation-wide cultural institution such as American baseball	<i>have two strikes against one</i>
2. Idioms of Institutionalized politeness	lexically expressed traditional forms of politeness	<i>may I ... X?</i>
3. Idioms of institutionalized detachment / indirectness	lexically expressed traditional forms indicating detachment / indirectness	<i>it seems that X ...</i>
4. Idioms of proposals ended as questions	lexically expressed traditional forms indicating an offer / proposal encoded in question form	<i>How about a drink?</i>
5. Idioms of institutionalized greeting	lexemically unalterable forms of greeting	<i>How do you do?</i>
6. Proverbial idioms with a moral	well recognized proverbs with a “moral”; traditionally expressed in a standard format with minimal changes	<i>Too many cooks spoil the broth</i>
7. Familiar quotations as idioms		<i>Brevity is the soul of wit</i>

8. Idiomaticity in institutionalized understatement	form that lessens the impact of ablunt statement	<i>it wasn't exactly my cup of tea</i>
9. Idiomaticity in institutionalized hyperbole	traditionally fixed forms describing a situation in obviously false (exaggerated) terms	<i>he won't even lift a finger</i>

In sum, the most valuable part of Makkai’s work concerns the identification of idioms on the basis of the various criteria commented on in the foregoing discussion. The use of the stratification grammar model makes his study an early example of a highly formal approach to idioms resulting in useful idiom categorizations and sub-categorizations on either structural or functional differences setting the basis for thesaurus-like Ecological lexicography. Idiomaticity is viewed as a language universal, a representation of phoricity, whereby signs in human languages point not only at their references but at other signs as well and through these at a series of networks of interrelated references as is the case with the phenomena of metaphor, anaphora and cataphora.

The list of literature

- 1.Katz, J.J. and P.M. Postal. Semantic Interpretation of Idioms and Sentences containing them. M.I.T. Research Laboratory of Electronics Quarterly Progress Report 70. 1963.
- 2.Katz, J.J. Compositionality, Idiomaticity and Lexical Substitution. In S. Anderson and P. Kiparsky (Eds.) A Festschrift for Morris Halle. New York: Holt, Rinehart and Winston. 1973
- 3.Crystal,1980 “ A first dictionary of linguistics and phonetics” London. Andre Deutsch
- 4.Makkai,, A.. (1972) Idiom Structure in English. The Hague:Mouton.